

Interband Transitions Are more Efficient than Plasmonic Excitation in the Ultrafast Melting of Electromagnetically-Coupled Au Nanoparticles

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Abstract

We investigated the effects of ultrafast laser excitation of Au nanoparticles (NPs) having strong interparticle electromagnetic coupling, by irradiating the NPs either at interband or plasmon-resonance wavelengths (13-100 J/m² fluence regime). We observed that interband excitation is significantly more efficient than plasmonic excitation in reshaping, coalescing and ultimately sublimating the NPs, despite the light-absorption cross-section of interband excitation being almost half that of plasmonic irradiation. We ascribed this to the different localization of radiation-induced heat sources in the strongly-coupled NPs in the two cases. Interband excitation induces homogeneous heat generation in Au, and so the conventional NP heating pathway is followed, eventually leading to overall melting, coalescence and ablation of Au. Plasmonic irradiation, on the other hand, promotes strong localization of the heat sources within small energetic hot spots, a fact that we suggest may lead to non-thermal effects that melt and reshape the NPs only on the local scale, leaving the system otherwise relatively unscathed.

Introduction

Metallic nanoparticles (NPs) and nanostructures with plasmonic properties are sensitive probes of relevant physical properties of matter on the local scale,^{1,2} and are widely exploited for chemical and biological sensing.³ During the early years of their investigation, the losses associated with the plasmon resonance were often regarded as unwanted spurious effects, until it was realized that metallic NPs can be successfully exploited as efficient converters of electromagnetic energy into heat at the nanoscale.⁴⁻⁶ Indeed, plasmonic heating has the potential advantage of acting on the typical scale of a few tens of nm, and of being remotely controlled by light. This has led to a large number of applications of noble-metal NPs and nanorods in photothermal therapy,⁷⁻¹⁰ nanowelding,¹¹⁻¹⁹ heat-assisted magnetic recording²⁰ and light based control of the morphology of nanostructures, typically their melting,

nanowelding or photofragmentation.^{21–32}

The mechanisms of the heat deposition in metal NPs has been extensively studied both from a theoretical^{33–44} and experimental^{45–51} points of view. Nonetheless, there are still many questions to be answered about the details of these mechanisms.

The role of localized surface plasmon resonances (LSPR) in thermoplasmonics is essentially to endow NPs with an enhanced cross section for electromagnetic-radiation absorption, σ_{abs} , at photon energies for which the parent material in its bulk form may exhibit a weaker interaction with light. The tunability of the LSPR as a function of the NP size, shape and dielectric environment^{52–56} provides, in turn, an efficient mechanism for tailoring the degree of interaction of EM radiation with the particles and hence for tailoring the heat dissipation. Nonetheless, in noble metals such as Au the absorption cross sections at wavelengths corresponding to interband excitation are often comparable with the cross sections associated with plasmonic resonances. In this respect, interesting differences arise between the two different cases in energy and spatial distribution of the excited electrons, especially the so-called hot electrons.⁵⁷ Irradiation with light at the LSPR wavelength typically yields highly-localized excitation in the so-called electromagnetic *hot spots*,⁵⁸ whereas interband-excited hot electrons are more homogeneously generated all across the NP volume. Furthermore, the LSPR is not an intrinsic property of the NP material, but stems from the spatial confinement of its electrons, whereas the interband transition is an intrinsic characteristic of the constituent material, weakly affected by spatial confinement. Indeed, it has been suggested recently that interband excitations may be more efficient than LSPR in promoting some photocatalytic activities of composite noble metal/semiconductor systems.⁵⁹ Such differences can be exploited for their different impact on the thermoplasmonic response.

We investigated the interaction of intense pulsed-laser radiation with ordered, supported, 2-dimensional (2D) arrays of near-field coupled Au NPs. The 2D arrays consisted of coherently-aligned chains of Au NPs with few-nm interparticle gaps, exhibiting a well-defined plasmonic

response at $\lambda = 600$ nm.

The arrays were irradiated with 50-fs laser pulses tuned at wavelengths spanning both the interband and the LSPR ranges. The heat-induced modifications were later assessed by atomic-force microscopy (AFM) and optical micro-spectrometry at equilibrium.

Interestingly, although the calculated absorption cross-section at plasmon wavelengths (σ_{abs}^{LSPR}) was 70% larger than its value at interband frequencies (σ_{abs}^{interb}), interband heating was much more efficient in inducing NP melting, re-aggregation and ultimately sublimation from the substrate. We propose an interpretation based on the different spatial distribution of the heat sources $q(\vec{r})$ within the NPs between the two different irradiation wavelengths. Interband excitation yields a more homogeneous heat distribution within the NPs which eventually leads to conventional thermodynamic heating. LSPR excitation leads instead to a strong concentration of extremely intense heat sources in the near-surface region, that promotes non-thermal melting effects that act only on a local scale and may therefore leave the NPs less affected.

Experiment

The samples consisted of self-organized 2D arrays of Au NPs deposited onto the surface of a nanopatterned LiF(110) single crystal.^{3,55} The arrays were fabricated depositing Au onto the self-organized nanometric uniaxial sawtooth pattern that develops upon high-temperature homoepitaxial growth onto LiF(110) substrates (Crystech GmbH).⁶⁰ ~ 4 nm of Au (Mateck GmbH, 99.99% purity) were deposited at room temperature in high vacuum ($p \approx 5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ mbar) by molecular beam epitaxy at 60° of incidence with respect to the surface normal, and the samples were subsequently annealed at $T=670$ K⁵⁵ in order to induce the thermal dewetting of the deposited metal.

Fig. 1 (top) shows an AFM image of the NP arrays ($2 \times 2 \mu\text{m}^2$). AFM images were acquired by means of a Multimode/Nanoscope IV system, Digital Instruments-Veeco microscope. The

image analysis was performed using the open-source software Gwyddion.⁶¹ We can observe a dense ensemble of NPs aligned along the nanogrooves of the substrate, so that the sample effectively consists of closely-spaced, coherently-oriented chains of Au NPs. For quantitative analysis purposes, the NPs were discriminated by means of digital threshold algorithms in order to deduce their mean areal density and extract the correspondent 2D pair correlation function (2D-PCF), reported in the inset of Fig. 1 ($240 \times 240 \text{ nm}^2$). The tendency of NPs to align along the substrate nanogrooves is apparent. The dominant, short-range periodicity of the 2D array in the direction parallel (perpendicular) to the Au NP chains is found to be $39 \pm 5 \text{ nm}$ ($26 \pm 4 \text{ nm}$). From the thickness of Au deposited and the NP density ($980 \pm 40 \text{ NP}/\mu\text{m}^2$), it is possible to deduce a mean NP volume around $4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ nm}^3$. The NP contours were fitted as ellipses in order to estimate their *in-plane* aspect ratio (AR=1.4), which means that the NPs are *coherently* elongated along the substrate grooves. If we schematize the NPs as prolate ellipsoids, their semiaxes transverse to, along the ripples and normal to the substrate read ($9 \pm 3, 13 \pm 4, 9 \pm 3$) nm.

In Fig. 1, bottom, we report the transmission spectrum of the Au NPs, measured with light linearly polarized along the NP-chain direction, incident normal to the surface. The strong dip at $\lambda \approx 595 \text{ nm}$ corresponds to the collective LSPR of the array.⁵⁵ The transmittance at the LSPR wavelength reads 0.53, whereas at $\lambda = 400 \text{ nm}$ it is 0.74.

The laser-irradiation was performed as follows: laser pulses with 50 fs duration, 500 Hz repetition rate and $100 \pm 40 \mu\text{m}$ and $250 \pm 50 \mu\text{m}$ spot diameters (respectively for $\lambda_{irr} = 400$ and 600 nm) were shone for 3 s (1500 pulses), on different pristine areas of the sample. The pulse fluences were varied from area to area, in order to systematically explore the effect of this variable on the deposition of heat in the system. We chose values of pulse fluence F_{pulse} which ranged from a minimum of 13 J/m^2 to a maximum of 100 J/m^2 (save for the lowest fluence, fluences have been rounded to the nearest 5 J/m^2). The laser wavelength was set to $\lambda_{irr} = 400, 600 \text{ nm}$ (grey markers in Fig. 1, bottom). Thus, 400-nm (600-nm) excitation corresponds to the interband (LSPR) spectral range.

Figure 1: Top: AFM image of the 2D array of Au NPs deposited on nanopatterned LiF ($2 \times 2 \mu\text{m}^2$). Inset: 2D pair correlation function of the NP array ($240 \times 240 \text{ nm}^2$). Bottom: transmission spectrum of the pristine Au NP array. The spectrum was measured with light polarized parallel to the NP chains, at normal incidence. The grey dots represent the wavelength values at which laser irradiation was performed in different experiments.

Figure 2: Left column: AFM images ($2 \times 2 \mu\text{m}^2$) of the NP arrays after irradiation with $\lambda_{irr} = 400 \text{ nm}$ radiation. Top to bottom, the mean pulse fluence was 13 J/m^2 , 25 J/m^2 , 50 J/m^2 and 75 J/m^2 . Top right: AFM image of the as-grown system. Right column: AFM images of the NP arrays after irradiation with $\lambda_{irr} = 600 \text{ nm}$ radiation. Top to bottom, the mean pulse fluence was 50 J/m^2 , 75 J/m^2 and 100 J/m^2 . Inset of AFM images: 2D pair correlation function of the respective NP array (lateral dimensions: $240 \times 240 \text{ nm}^2$).

The laser beams used for the melting and probe of the 2D arrays were produced by a single Ti:Sapphire based femtosecond laser system. This system consists of a Ti:Sapphire oscillator producing 20 fs pulses with a frequency of 80 MHz, a part of whose output is used to seed a chirped pulse amplifier which in turn generates 4 mJ, 35 fs pulses centered at 800 nm with a repetition rate of 1 kHz. An optical parametric amplifier (OPA) is then used to convert part of the amplifier output into tunable radiation. The melting laser pulses were either the second harmonic of the amplifier or the output of the OPA. The white light probe pulse (350-800 nm) is generated by focusing 3 μJ of the amplifier radiation into a rotating CaF_2 crystal.

The sample morphology resulting from the high-fluence irradiation was then assessed by means of AFM, and the data were compared with the corresponding pristine data. Transmission spectra were performed on the irradiated areas by means of a home-built microspectrometer with 10 μm -diameter areal acceptance.

In Fig. 2 we report a set of AFM images measured on irradiated areas. The left column reports images recorded following irradiation with $\lambda_{irr} = 400$ nm. Top to bottom, the pulse fluence increased from 13 J/m^2 to 75 J/m^2 . In the right column, images corresponding to $\lambda_{irr} = 600$ nm irradiation are reported. Top to bottom, the pulse fluence increased from 50 J/m^2 to 100 J/m^2 . Images recorded for the same pulse energy are arranged side-by-side, in order to ease their comparison. In the top right corner, an image of the pristine system is reported, again for comparison. Irradiation at $\lambda_{irr} = 600$ nm with 13 J/m^2 and 25 J/m^2 fluence led to undetectable variations of both morphology and optical response.

Let us consider the images corresponding to interband irradiation ($\lambda_{irr} = 400$ nm). For $F_{pulse} = 13$ J/m^2 , we observe minor variations, apart from the appearance of a few large aggregates, randomly located on the sample. Quantitative analysis shows that the mean in-plane AR has decreased to 1.2, while the arrays show a diminished degree of order, testified by the presence of weaker structures in the 2D-PCF with respect to the pristine case (inset). The NP density now reads ≈ 500 NP/ μm^2 .

For $F_{pulse} = 25 \text{ J/m}^2$, significant modifications begin to appear. The NPs have clearly become much larger in size, and their aspect ratio is now around unity. Their areal density has strongly decreased to $300 \text{ NP}/\mu\text{m}^2$, and the 2D-PCF shows a weak, isotropic correlation ring, that indicates that the NPs have lost their pristine arrangement.

Increasing further the pulse energy to 50 J/m^2 the NPs become slightly larger in size, their areal density further decreases to roughly $215 \text{ NP}/\mu\text{m}^2$ and they completely lose their positional correlation; large portions of uncovered substrate start to appear. Finally, for $F_{pulse} = 75 \text{ J/m}^2$, the AFM data mostly show the bare substrate, meaning that Au has been ablated from the surface. The substrate was not significantly damaged since the nanogrooves of the LiF surface are still clearly observable.

For $\lambda_{irr} = 600 \text{ nm}$, the system evolution is remarkably different. For $F_{pulse} = 13 \text{ J/m}^2$ and 25 J/m^2 no detectable variations were observed. At $F_{pulse} = 50 \text{ J/m}^2$, a few large agglomerates appear, whereas the majority of the array is only weakly affected by the laser. The AR of the particles has decreased to 1.2, the areal density is roughly $1000 \text{ NP}/\mu\text{m}^2$, and the positional correlation and size have been largely preserved. Increasing the pulse fluence to 75 J/m^2 a further slight decrease of the mean aspect ratio to 1.1 is observed, accompanied by a drop of NP density to roughly $750 \text{ NP}/\mu\text{m}^2$. Several aggregates have now appeared and the NPs have become slightly larger in size, though the arrays have preserved a fair degree of positional order. For $F_{pulse} = 100 \text{ J/m}^2$, the aspect ratio has reached unity, and the NPs clearly show widespread signs of aggregation. Their areal density has dropped to roughly $500 \text{ NP}/\mu\text{m}^2$ and the systems shows just a weak residual degree of spatial correlation.

In Fig.3, we report micro-transmission spectra selectively recorded in the irradiated areas after the irradiation was conducted (normal incidence, polarization direction along the NP chains). The optical micro-transmission spectra were measured with a home-built setup featuring a pulsed Xe lamp as the light source (Hamamatsu L9455). A $20\times$ objective is employed to magnify the sample, and the transmitted light is detected by a fiber-

Figure 3: Top panel: transmission spectra of the Au NP after irradiation with pulse of energy 25 J/m^2 , 50 J/m^2 and 75 J/m^2 at $\lambda = 400$ nm (blue, green and orange symbols, respectively). The black line is the unperturbed spectrum. Bottom panel: transmission spectra of the Au NP after irradiation with pulse of energy 75 J/m^2 and 100 J/m^2 at $\lambda = 600$ nm (orange and red symbols, respectively). The black line is the unperturbed spectrum.

coupled Ocean Optics USB2000+ spectrometer. The fiber input acts as the virtual pinhole, effectively accepting radiation coming from an area with 10 μm diameter on the sample. In the top (bottom) panel, we report the data recorded following interband (plasmonic) irradiation. In both graphs, the pristine transmission spectrum is reported as the continuous black line. For interband irradiation, we report the spectra measured for $F_{pulse} = 25 \text{ J}/\text{m}^2$, 50 J/m^2 and 75 J/m^2 (blue, green and orange markers, respectively). The gradual weakening, narrowing and blueshift of the plasmonic dip with increasing F_{pulse} is apparent. The gradual Au ablation leads to a weakening absorption, as expected. The counterintuitive fact that the LSPR blueshifts even though the NPs become larger in size is due to the fact that the

LSPR in the pristine system is strongly redshifted due to the interparticle electromagnetic coupling.⁶² The melting and coalescence of the NPs leads to a loss of positional order, hence a weakening of the near-field, and consequent blueshift of the LSPR. For $F_{pulse} = 75 \text{ J/m}^2$, the transmission spectrum resembles the spectrally-flat response expected from a dielectric slab, confirming the almost total ablation of Au.

For $\lambda_{irr} = 600 \text{ nm}$, at $F_{pulse} = 75 \text{ J/m}^2$ we observe a slight blueshift and narrowing of the plasmonic peak, whereas for fluence of 100 J/m^2 also a gradual drop of absorption is observed. The results are clearly due to the decrease of the AR of the NPs, the gradual loss of positional order, and some evaporation of metallic material. The transmission data essentially agree with the picture drawn by AFM, in particular they underline the very different efficiency of interband and plasmonic heating in inducing irreversible system alterations.

Discussion

The irreversible changes that we observe are clearly due to the sudden heating by the laser pulse of the NPs array and its subsequent evolution (melting, coalescence, ablation). In order to understand which processes are at play, it is however paramount to estimate the maximum temperature achieved by the Au aggregates. Indeed, whereas it can be safely inferred that NP melting *must* have occurred in order for NPs to coalesce and assume a spherical shape,²² there are a number of processes occurring in NPs at sub-melting temperature that can affect their morphology (*e.g.* surface melting or non-thermal melting^{14,25,63}).

Since the duration of the laser pulse is much shorter than the typical time scales for the dissipation of thermal energy to the environment, the maximum NP temperature, under the hypothesis of *homogeneous heating*, can be estimated, according to Ref. 64, as:

$$\Delta T_{max} = \frac{\sigma_{abs} F}{V \rho_{Au} c_{Au}} \quad (1)$$

where V is the NP volume, ρ_{Au} and c_{Au} are the gold density and specific heat, F is the

experimental laser fluence and σ_{abs} is the absorption cross section of a unit cell of the array. This model assumes that all the energy absorbed from the electromagnetic field is used to homogeneously heat all of the gold in the nanostructure, and that no modification of the dielectric function of Au occurs over the duration of the excitation pulse.

The absorption cross-section σ_{abs} was obtained by means of Rigorous Coupled Wave Analysis (RCWA). RCWA is a technique which can well reproduce the optical response of periodic structures. The system geometry was set up according to the AFM data of the pristine sample (see Fig.4B). The simulation unit cell was a rectangle with its long side along the NP chains having $39 \times 26 \text{ nm}^2$ area and periodic boundary conditions in the x-, y-directions. The ripples angle with respect to the surface normal was set at 22° .⁶⁵ The NP were modelled as ellipsoids truncated by the substrate facets, and their shape was slightly adapted from the simplified hypothesis of prolate ellipsoids ((x, y, z) semi-axes (12.5, 17.5, 13) nm, truncated at the intersection with the substrate) in order to better match the experimental extinction. Clearly, no shape/size/positional disorder could be included.

The input source was a plane wave with polarization along the ripples and normal incidence. In terms of output, the RCWA method can return total reflection, transmission and absorption under the normalization condition at any investigated wavelength. Reference dielectric functions of Au and LiF were employed.^{66,67}

In Fig.4A we report the simulated absorbance (blue line), compared with the experimental one (symbols). The theoretical curve reproduces with high accuracy the main features of the experimental data. The red line represents to the corresponding σ_{abs} as a function of wavelength, yielding $\sigma_{abs}(400\text{nm}) = 2.03 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ m}^2$ and $\sigma_{abs}(600\text{nm}) = 3.45 \cdot 10^{-16} \text{ m}^2$. Substituting these σ_{abs} values into Eq. 1, we obtain the theoretical maximum temperature increases reported in Table 1.

For $\lambda = 600 \text{ nm}$ irradiation, the calculated temperature increase was 1700 K, 2500 K and 3400 K for $F_{pulse} = 50 \text{ J/m}^2$, 75 J/m^2 and 100 J/m^2 , respectively, whereas for interband

Table 1: Calculated maximum temperature increase ΔT_{max} for irradiation at $\lambda = 400$ nm and $\lambda = 600$ nm for different values of laser-pulse fluence. Fluences (apart from the lowest fluence) are rounded to the nearest 5 J/m² and temperatures are rounded to the nearest 50 K. Temperature values that go above the Au bulk melting temperatures are marked with an asterisk.

	13 J/m ²	25 J/m ²	50 J/m ²	75 J/m ²	100 J/m ²
	$\Delta T(K)$				
$\lambda = 400$ nm	250	500	1050*	1550*	
$\lambda = 600$ nm			1700*	2550*	3400*

irradiation the maximum temperature increase is roughly 1550 K for 75 J/m², scaling linearly with F_{pulse} (we notice that these values are calculated for the pristine morphology; strictly speaking, they are rigorously valid only for the first pulse of the 1500 impinging on the system. However, the main findings of our work are not significantly affected. Furthermore, this conclusion remains valid even after the propagation of the errors due to the uncertainties in the spot sizes). It clearly appears that, according to the results of Eq. 1 for *homogeneous* heating, larger temperature increases should be obtained for plasmonic irradiation rather than interband irradiation. Thus, the fact that an interband excitation with $F_{pulse} = 75$ J/m² (theoretical $\Delta T \approx 1550$ K) is sufficient to almost completely ablate the Au NPs whereas analogous or even larger fluences left the system almost unscathed upon excitation at λ_{LSPR} points to a more complex picture.

In the literature, the observation of an analogous effect was accounted for in terms of the different electronic specific heat between interband and plasmonic irradiation.⁶⁸ The experiments in Ref. 68 were however performed with ns pulses, and the occurrence of several excitation/deexcitation cycles within a single pulse was instrumental to the interpretation in terms of electronic specific heat. The fact that we employ much shorter pulses seems to rule out such an explanation in the present case, implying that other phenomena must be at play.

Analogously, it might be argued that the temperature-induced plasmon bleaching can be responsible for a decrease in σ_{abs} , whereas a laser-induced absorption might have enhanced

Figure 4: Panel A: experimental (symbols) and calculated (blue line) absorbance of the NP arrays . Calculated absorption cross section σ_{abs} for a single unit cell of the 2D periodic array (red line). Panel B: left (right) side, top to bottom: calculated 3D maps of the local electric field intensity on the NP surface for interband (plasmonic) excitation and cross section along the NP long axis for interband (plasmonic) irradiation. Panel C: left (right) side: calculated 3D maps of the local electric field intensity on the NP surface for interband (plasmonic) excitation in the case of *isolated* NPs.

it in the interband range. However, such effects typically occur over time scales longer than the excitation pulse duration, hence should have minor influence on the system.

In this respect, we can however notice that significant differences arise in the local distribution of the electric field \vec{E} in the NPs between the plasmonic and interband cases;

calculations of the near-field maps for these two conditions are reported in Fig.4B. The near field images were determined through the Finite Integration technique (FIT) where the employment of a tetrahedral mesh could guarantee a proper electric field distribution even over curved structures. On the left (right) side of Fig.4B we report the simulations performed for incident radiation with $\lambda = 400$ nm ($\lambda = 600$ nm). The top panels of Fig. 4B represent the 3D near-field distribution at the NP surface with periodic boundary conditions, whereas the bottom panels represent cross sections of the electric-field magnitude on a plane bisecting the NP along their long axis and normal to the substrate. In Fig.4C we report analogous calculations performed for the isolated-NP case. The color scale of the 3D distributions is the same for the interband and the plasmonic case.

The striking differences between the interband and plasmonic cases are the different intensity of the maximum field at the NP surface, at least twofold larger for plasmonic excitation, and the different degree of uniformity of the field over the entire NP volume. Indeed, whereas the electric-field magnitude is relatively homogeneous for interband excitation, its magnitude becomes strongly inhomogeneous for plasmonic excitation, where it peaks within the small NP volume directly facing the interparticle gaps. Since the heat sources are related to $\vec{E}(\vec{\mathbf{r}})$ through the relation $q(\vec{\mathbf{r}}) = \frac{\omega}{2} \text{Im}(\varepsilon(\omega)) \varepsilon_0 |\vec{E}(\vec{\mathbf{r}})|^2$, there is a corresponding difference in their spatial distribution within the NP.

In the time regime when no heat dissipation from the NP to the environment has taken place, the interband irradiation promotes the generation of heat sources homogeneously distributed within the NP. Under these conditions it is reasonable to assume that the heating process proceeds through the conventional pathway of hot-electron generation, homogenization of the electron gas over the NP, electronic thermalization and subsequent lattice heating. Thus the theoretically estimated ΔT is evenly achieved throughout the NP, thereby justifying the experimental observations (aggregation, melting and ablation).

For the plasmonic case, where the total amount of energy deposited in the NP is larger than the interband case due to the larger absorption cross section, the key factor in determining

the system evolution can be the electric-field spatial distribution, hence $q(\vec{\mathbf{r}})$. However, for the heating-source distribution to have an impact on the morphological evolution, the melting phenomena must have taken place before the temperature equilibration of the electron gas within the NP has occurred. A fitting hypothesis is that the highly-concentrated plasmonic heating leads to an ultrafast non-thermal melting within the highest-excitation volume. In this case, the energy deposited could be efficiently dissipated by local Au ablation from the NP surfaces, that leaves their shape only weakly altered⁶⁹ or by the formation of a plasma in the hot-spot volume due to photoionization, impact ionization and/or strong-field photoemission.^{70,71} Indeed, the fluences used here are consistent with the threshold proposed by Boulais for the transition from an absorption to the near-field regime in Au nanorods (30 J/m²). Such local ablation of material, over the whole laser-shot sequence, leads to slight blueshift of the plasmonic resonance and ultimately to its weakening (see Fig. 3). Under the present experimental conditions, we cannot assess whether such changes occur upon a single/few pulses or after the accumulation of all the pulse sequence: in the former case, a self-limiting effect might be at play, since σ_{abs}^{LSPR} can be modified following the first few pulses. The effects related to the high concentration of heating sources should disappear in absence of strong electromagnetic coupling (see calculations in Fig. 4C for isolated NPs).

Further experimental support for asymmetric plasmonic heating of noble metal nanostructures can be found in works describing the threading of chains of gold nanospheres^{17,29} or nanorods^{18,19} by locally melting the gold into the regions between very closely spaced nanoparticles. These works are further evidence that morphological changes occur in the hot spots before the heat can be evenly propagated throughout the NP. A few potentially interesting aspects of our experiment in comparison with other plasmonic systems can be pointed out, particularly with respect to nanorods and/or colloidal systems, of high interest for thermoplasmonics and light-matter interaction.^{72,73} Within this framework, our experiments on supported NPs might provide different insights in the laser-induced melting phenomena since NPs are physically bound to a substrate, that limits their mobility and may

prevent threading under conditions where this occurs in colloidal systems.^{17,29} On the other hand, NPs are less sensitive probes of the morphological evolution under laser irradiation than nanorods, where the AR-dependence of the LSPR is much stronger. Also, small NPs possess a more thermodynamically-stable shape, hence tend to experience coalescence upon melting, rather than photofragmentation.

Conclusion

Summarizing, we have reported an experimental investigation of the laser-induced heating and reshaping of Au NPs within strongly coupled 2D arrays. The 2D arrays were irradiated with sequences of 50-fs laser pulses at interband ($\lambda = 400$ nm) or LSPR ($\lambda = 600$ nm) wavelength, with pulse fluence in the 13 J/m² to 100 J/m² range. Although calculations and measurements show that the absorption cross-section of the NP σ_{abs}^{LSPR} is 70% larger for plasmonic irradiation rather than for interband irradiation, we observed that interband heating was significantly more efficient in inducing the NP melting all over the array, and ultimately even the sublimation of Au from the substrate. We interpreted this result as the effect of the different localization of the heat sources $q(\vec{r})$ in the NP during the laser irradiation. Upon interband excitation, calculations shows that there is a more homogeneous distribution of heat sources within the NPs, that subsequently leads to homogeneous NP heating that can exceed the bulk melting temperature and lead to NP melting, re-aggregation, and even sublimation. In the plasmonic-irradiation case, the strong electromagnetic coupling of neighbouring Au NPs leads to a very strong localization of the electric field in the small NP volumes facing the interparticle gaps. This possibly promotes non-thermal effects that locally melt/reshape the NPs without leading to their full melting, reaggregation etc.

The difference between plasmonic and interband irradiation is particularly pronounced due to the dense packing of NPs in the array, that effectively promotes a significant difference in the heat-source localization within the particles. This shows the possibility to fine-tune

the heating/reshaping efficiency of nanoscale metal objects by means of laser pulses based not only on their wavelength but also on the engineering of the local environment of the nano-objects. Beyond this, accurate design of nanostructure architectures can be instrumental for creating exotic states of matter (*e.g.* non-thermal molten solids) within metallic nanostructures and their near environment.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge support from the Ministero dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca (PRIN NEWLI, n.2015CL3APH) and from the Compagnia di San Paolo (proj. PanLab).

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